

UNICO
I+D 6G

D1.1 State of the art review and networking requirements for 6G XR v0.1

Fecha de Publicación: 31/03/2023

**[6GOPENVERSO-NET] State of the art review
and networking requirements for 6G XR
[6GOPENVERSO] [6GOPENVERSO-NET]**

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

**Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia**

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	PTx
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Nivel de diseminación	Público
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

P	Público
P	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
R	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
C	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios

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3 Lista de Acrónimos

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth generation cellular networks
6DoF	6 degrees of freedom
6G	Sixth generation cellular networks
AF	Application Function
AR	Augmented Reality
AS	Application Server
gNB	Next Generation Node B
DL	Downlink
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
MCU	Multipoint Control Unit
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MR	Mixed Reality
NaaS	Network as a Service
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Networks
SFU	Selective Forwarding Unit
UE	User equipment
UL	Uplink
URLLC	Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication
UPF	User Plane Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	eXtended Reality

4 Resumen Ejecutivo

This deliverable presents the state of art for XR services and its requirements of the 6G-OPENVERSO-NET project, specifically tasks T1.1 and T1.2 res, with the ultimate intent of supporting the validation of the XR services that are developed in 6G-OPENVERSO-HOLO.

5. Introduction

Extended reality (XR) refers to an emerging technology that encompasses a spectrum of immersive experiences, blending the physical and virtual worlds. Its use cases are not limited to consumer applications like gaming, but also include enterprise, institutions, and manufacturing. XR will influence the way people play, work, learn, and interact with each other. XR includes three main categories: virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR). The potential applications of extended reality are vast and span across various industries. In the gaming and entertainment sector, XR offers unprecedented levels of immersion, transporting users into virtual worlds and enabling them to participate in interactive experiences. It also has significant potential in education and training, providing realistic simulations for hands-on learning experiences, medical training, and skill development in fields such as engineering and aviation. In healthcare, XR can revolutionize patient care by enabling remote consultations, surgical planning, and therapy sessions in immersive environments. Architectural firms and interior designers can use XR to create virtual walkthroughs of building designs, allowing clients to experience and make changes to their projects before construction begins. Furthermore, XR has the potential to enhance communication and collaboration, as users can interact with virtual objects and each other in shared virtual spaces, regardless of their physical locations. As technology continues to evolve and become more accessible, the possibilities for extended reality are limited only by our imagination.

XR will play an important role in 5G advanced and 6G networks. Meanwhile, the successful adoption of XR requires support from the underlying wireless systems. The XR traffic characteristics include quasi-periodic traffic in large chunks, irregular intervals and variable size, high data rate including uplink (UL) for AR services, simultaneous transmission of 3D video stream, and control data over the same end to end connection. In addition, other key characteristics include low power consumption to extend battery life and minimize heat dissipation for user comfort, and tight delay and reliability constraints to meet user Quality of Experience (QoE). Those

demands made XR to not perfectly fit into the existing classification of 5G applications and services, but typically fit the delivery requirements of eMBB and URLLC together. 5G technology improved access to high quality video, but 5G-Advanced will offer more immersive user experiences, and 6G development is working to provide more holographic experiences, digital twins, localization, and sensing are also being enhanced to support XR.

6. State of the Art

6.1 Different Types of Realities

XR combines three types of realities: Virtual reality, Augmented reality, and Mixed reality.

- **Virtual Reality (VR):** It is designed to mimic the visual and audio sensory stimuli of the real world to an observer or user as they move within the limits defined by the application. For the simulated visual component, the user should wear a head mounted display (HMD), while wearing headphones for the audio component. From the user's perspective, to ensure that items and sound sources remain consistent with the user's movements, some form of head and motion tracking is required.
- **Augmented Reality (AR):** When a user is provided with artificially generated items, or content upon their current environment.
- **Mixed Reality (MR):** Illusion is created by inserting virtual elements into the physical scene so that these elements are part of the real scene.

Besides this, other related and relevant concepts are described below.

- **Immersion:** The sense of being surrounded by the virtual environment.
- **Presence:** Providing the feeling of being physically located in a virtual environment.
- **Occlusion:** The phenomenon when one object in a 3D space is blocking another object from being viewed.
- **Extended reality (XR):** It includes AR, MR and VR and the areas interpolated among them. it refers to all real-and-virtual combined environments and human-machine interactions generated by computer technology and wearables.

Figure 6.2.1: Different types of realities

6.2 Quality of experience for XR

The quality of experience for XR depends on the concepts of presence, age of content and interaction and roundtrip delays; described by the below definitions.

- I. **Presence** is defined as providing the user with the feeling of being physically and spatially located in an environment. Presence is divided into 2 types: a) cognitive presence, as the presence of one's mind' and b) perceptive Presence, as the presence of one's senses, i.e., tricking the user's senses, sights or sounds. The presence can be broken down into three broad categories: a) visual presence, b) auditory presence, and c) sensory or haptic presence. There are four components relevant for feeling present:
 - A. The illusion of being in a stable spatial place.

- B. The illusion of self-embodiment.
 - C. The illusion of physical interaction.
 - D. The illusion of social communication.
- II. **Interaction Delay** is defined as the time difference between the moment the user action is initiated and the time an action is considered by the content creation engine. For example, in the gaming context, this is the time between the moment the user interacts with the game and the moment the game engine processes response.
 - III. **Age of Content** is the time difference between the moment a content is created and the time it is presented to the user.
 - IV. **The roundtrip interaction delay** is the sum of the Age of Content and the Interaction Delay.

The four following categories are typically considered with respect to roundtrip interaction delay, according to [1] :

Application	Roundtrip interaction latency
Ultra-Low-Latency applications	50ms
Low-Latency applications	100ms
Moderate latency applications	200ms
Non-critical latency applications	>200ms

Table 6.3.1: XR application requirements [1]

6.3 XR Delivery in 5G System

The XR delivery includes the following services:

- I. **Download:** XR includes media and experience related traffic is in the downlink (DL) direction, i.e., downloadable.

- II. **(Passive) Streaming:** All media related traffic is in the downlink and is not triggering any uplink (UL) traffic.
- III. **Interactive (Streaming):** The traffic is in the downlink, but certain traffic is uplink, e.g, XR Viewer Pose information.
- IV. **Conversational:** The experience is generated, shared and consumed in real-time from two or more participants with conversational latency requirements.
- V. **Split Compute/Rendering:** The network function runs XR engine to support processing and pre-rendering of immersive scenes where the delivery is split into more than one connection.

6.4 5G System and Radio Functionalities for XR

The integration of XR applications within the 5G System is approached following the model of 5G Media Streaming as defined in (3GPP). UEs use a 5G-XR aware application to make use of a 5G-XR client and network functions using network interfaces and APIs, as shown in Figure 6.5.1.

Figure 6.5.1: 5G-XR functions integrated in 5G system [1]

The three main functions of 5G system for XR applications are defined below:

- I. **5G-XR AF:** An Application Function (AF) dedicated to 5G-XR Services. It provides various control functions to the XR Session Handler on the UE and/or to the 5G-XR Application Provider.

- II. **5G-XR AS:** An Application Server (AS) dedicated to 5G-XR Services and hosting 5G-XR media and media functions.
- III. **5G-XR Client:** UE internal function dedicated to 5G-XR Services.

5G-XR AF and 5G-XR AS are initially considered Data Network (DN) functions and communicate with the UE via N6, N3 and Uu as defined in [1].

Figure 6.5.2: 5G-XR Interfaces and Architecture [1]

The basic detailed XR architecture integrated in 5G is shown in Figure 6.5.2.

- I. **5G-XR Client on UE:** Receiver of 5G-XR session data that may be accessed through well-defined interfaces/APIs by the 5G-XR Aware Application. The 5G-XR Client contains two sub-functions:
 - A. **XR Session Handler:** The UE's function that communicates with the 5G-XR AF to establish, control and support the delivery of an XR session.
 - B. **XR Engine:** The UE's function that communicates with the 5G-XR Application Server to get access to XR related data.
- II. **5G-XR Aware Application:** Establishes XR sessions by making use of 5G-XR Client and network functions using interfaces and APIs. It controls the 5G-XR Client.
- III. **5G-XR Application Provider:** External XR application provider that makes use of 5G-XR client and network functionalities.

6.5 Quality-of-Service in 5G

The 5G QoS model supports both:

- I. QoS Flows that require guaranteed flow bit rate (GBR QoS Flows).
- II. QoS Flows that do not require guaranteed flow bit rate (Non-GBR QoS Flows).

In the 5G System, each Flow is identified by QoS Flow ID (QFI). Within each QoS Flow, its assigned User Plane traffic in the same Protocol Data Unit (PDU) Session receives the same traffic forwarding treatment (e.g., scheduling, admission threshold). The QoS Flow may either be “GBR”, “Non-GBR” or “Delay Tolerant GBR” depending on its QoS profile.

6.6 Technical challenges for XR in 5G NR

XR applications typically require larger volumes of data to be transmitted quickly while also adhering to strict packet delay limits and ensuring reliability. This places XR applications in a category that falls between broadband (eMBB) and ultra reliable low latency communication (URLLC) service classes. Unlike other types of traffic, XR traffic exhibits characteristics depending on the specific use cases involved, i.e., a mix of periodic and random parts. The potentially significant stream of data presents a challenge as it requires scheduling and must meet stringent requirements for radio latency and reliability. However, achieving these goals often comes at the expense of network efficiency due to the tradeoff between data rate, latency and reliability. Consequently, existing radio operations such as radio resource management may not be optimally designed to integrate XR services given their traffic characteristics and performance demands. A summary of the challenges facing the XR applications deployment in 5G networks is provided below:

- 1) **High Data Rates and Throughput:** XR applications require high data rates to provide a seamless and immersive experience. Although 5G promises high data rates, the volume of data required to stream high-quality XR content can still strain the network.
- 2) **Low Latency:** XR applications are heavily dependent on low latency to maintain a sense of presence and prevent motion sickness. The delay results in a noticeable lag between the user actions and their corresponding responses in the XR environment.
- 3) **Network Coverage and Reliability:** XR applications often demand continuous and stable network coverage, especially for mobile XR experiences.

- 4) **Edge Computing and Processing:** To address the latency challenges, XR systems can benefit from leveraging edge computing. This is done by offloading some processing tasks to the network edge.
- 5) **High Bandwidth Requirements:** XR content demands massive bandwidth for delivering high-resolution, 3D content to users. This places significant strain on the 5G network infrastructure.
- 6) **Battery Life:** XR devices have limited battery life. 5G's energy efficiency improvements are helpful, but the high data demands of XR applications can still drain the device's battery quickly.
- 7) **Network Congestion:** In densely populated areas or during peak usage times, 5G networks can face congestion issues, affecting the performance of XR applications. In addition, the 5G network is designed to have enough resources in downlink direction while some XR applications require enough resources in uplink direction such as holographic communication. This results in congestion in the uplink direction and demands innovative solutions to avoid and decrease its severity.
- 8) **Interoperability:** XR systems consist of various devices, platforms, and operating systems. To ensure seamless experience, the interoperability between different XR devices and 5G networks is essential and can be challenging.

As a result of the above mentioned technical challenges, there is a need to develop new network architecture that incorporate new technologies and functions that can better serve XR applications.

7 XR Use cases

This section presents both the use cases defined by 3GPP and the proposed use cases.

7.1 Use cases defined by 3GPP

The below table summarizes the use cases defined by 3GPP (3GPP TR 26.928) with its corresponding type and delivery. The use cases defined are differentiated according to the application.

No	Use Case	Type	Delivery
1	3D Image Messaging	AR	Upload and Download
2	AR Sharing	AR, MR	Local, Messaging Download and Upload
3	Streaming of Immersive 6DoF	VR	Streaming Interactive Split
4	Emotional Streaming	2D, AR and VR	Streaming Interactive, Split
5	Untethered Immersive Online Gaming	VR	Streaming, Interactive, Split
6	Immersive Game Spectator Mode	VR	Streaming, Split
7	Real-time 3D Communication	3D, AR	Conversational
8	AR guided assistant at remote location (industrial services)	2D video with dynamic AR rendering of graphics	Local, Streaming, Interactive, Conversational
9	Police Critical Mission with AR	AR, VR	Local, Streaming, Interactive, Conversational, Group Communication

10	Online shopping from a catalog – downloading	AR	Download
11	Real-time communication with the shop assistant	AR	Interactive, Conversational
12	360-degree conference meeting	AR, MR, VR	Conversational
13	3D shared experience	AR, MR, VR	Conversational
14	6DOF VR conferencing	VR	Interactive, Conversational
15	XR Meeting	AR,VR,XR	Interactive conversational
16	Convention / Poster Session	AR, VR, MR	Interactive conversational
17	AR animated avatar calls	AR	Conversational
18	Online shopping from a catalog – downloading	AR	Download
19	Front-facing camera video multi-party calls	AR	Conversational

20	AR Streaming with Localization Registry	AR, Social AR	Streaming, Interactive, Conversational
21	Immersive Streaming with 6DoF Social Interaction	VR and Social VR	Streaming interactive conversational split
22	5G Online Gaming Party	VR	Streaming, Interactive, Split, D2D
23	Spatial Shared Data	AR	Streaming Interactive Conversational Split

Table 7.1.1: Summary of use cases defined by 3GPP [2]

This below table maps the use cases and scenarios for XR based on the underlying offered functionalities, the nature of the communication, interactivity and real-time requirements.

Core Use Cases and Scenarios	Use Cases
Offline Sharing of 3D Objects	Use Case 1: 3D Image Messaging Use Case 2: AR Sharing Use Case 10: Online shopping from a catalog – downloading

<p>Real-time XR Sharing</p>	<p>Use Case 7: Real-time 3D Communication</p> <p>Use Case 8: AR guided assistant at remote location (industrial services)</p> <p>Use Case 11: Real-time communication with the shop assistant</p> <p>Use Case 17: AR animated avatar calls</p> <p>Use Case 23: 5G Shared Spatial Data</p>
<p>XR Multimedia Streaming</p>	<p>Use Case 3: Streaming of Immersive 6DoF</p> <p>Use Case 4: Emotional Streaming</p> <p>Use Case 20: AR Streaming with Localization Register.</p> <p>Use Case 21: Immersive 6DoF Streaming with Social Interaction.</p>
<p>Online XR Gaming</p>	<p>Use Case 5: Untethered Immersive Online Gaming</p> <p>Use Case 6: Immersive Game Spectator Mode</p> <p>Use Case 22: 5G Online Gaming party</p>
<p>XR Mission Critical</p>	<p>Use Case 9: Police Mission Critical with AR</p>
<p>XR Conference</p>	<p>Use Case 12: 360-degree conference meeting</p> <p>Use Case 13: 3D shared experience</p> <p>Use Case 14: 6DOF VR conferencing</p> <p>Use Case 15: XR Meeting</p> <p>Use Case 16: Convention / Poster Session</p>

Spatial Audio Multiparty Call	Use Case 18: AR avatar multi-party calls Use Case 19: Front-facing camera video multi-party calls
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Table 7.1.2: Mapping of use cases and their scenarios [2]

7.1.1 Offline Sharing of 3D Objects

By looking at the Offline Sharing scenario as a way for sharing 3D models/objects and 3D MR scenes amongst UEs. The scenario is described in Figure. 7.1.1, where UE A shares a 3D static/dynamic object with UE B and the 3D object can be a stored object downloaded by UE A from the cloud or captured by the device using, for example, a depth camera. UE B can then render this object in the surrounding reality using an MR rendering engine. It can then capture the rendered MR scene and send it back to UE A.

Figure 7.1.1: Offline Sharing 3D Objects and MR Scenes [2]

7.1.2 Real-time XR Sharing

Fig. 7.1.2. illustrates the scenario for Real-time XR Sharing, where a UE B is a device capable of XR rendering, such as AR glasses, or a mobile phone that is sending a real-time video stream of the XR experience to UE A. UE B rendered the captured XR experience. The XR experience includes capture of 3D objects in a

2D scene and (real-time) 3D (static/dynamic) object placement in a 2D scene, overlay video, avatars, etc., that may be downloaded from the cloud, or sent by UE A to UE B.

Figure 7.1.2: Real-time sharing of XR content [2]

7.1.3 XR Multimedia Streaming

This scenario covers live and on-demand streaming of XR multimedia streams, which include 2D or Volumetric video streams that are rendered in XR with binaural audio. In Figure. 7.1.3, the UE receives input from handheld controllers, hand gestures, and biometric readings which are communicated to the content server to control the receiving and rendering of the type of stream in use. A Spatial Computing Server is used by XR; as it is capable of register, compute, update and recall the spatial configuration of their surroundings.

Figure 7.1.3: XR Multimedia Streaming [2]

7.1.4 Online XR Gaming

In the Online XR Gaming use case (Figure 7.1.4), a game server is capable of serving several online game players. Each player's UE receives a stream of the live game from the game server and sends control signals such as handheld controller inputs, biometric readings and motion as required by the gameplay back to the server that influences the game play. Other users may join the live game in spectator mode and can receive the stream from the perspective of an active player or an spectator view independent of other players.

Figure 7.1.4: Online XR Gaming [2]

7.1.5 XR Mission Critical

In this use case, a team is equipped with mission gear that is connected to a centralized control center; while the UE represents a single team member. There can be more than one device included in the mission gear, such as AR glasses, a 360-degree helmet-mounted camera, a microphone, binaural audio headphones and other sensors. The role of mission support is taken by the Control Center in Figure 7.1.5 (conference server) providing XR graphics such as maps, text, location pointers of other team members or other objects/people in the surrounding area. The mixed audio of the team members, as well as audio from the Control Centre, is also delivered to the UE to aid team communication and coordination.

Figure 7.1.5: XR Mission Critical [2]

7.1.6 XR Conference

The application of the XR Conference scenario can include multiple physically co-located and remote users. The shared conference space can be one of the three types: 1) a physical space shared by local participants, 2) a virtual space that has the same layout as the physical space so that the physically present (local) and remote participants have a similar experience while moving in the space, and 3) a virtual space that is retrieved from an AS. The UE's functionality can be split into two parts: one for user media capture and one for rendering. Those functions may be integrated within a single device (e.g., a smartphone) possibly augmented by peripheral devices like a wireless camera; or, alternatively, be separated, e.g., using a dedicated capture device (like a camera) and XR rendering device (like AR Glasses, mobile phone, VR HMD, holographic display, etc.). The required video processing is made on either the media server or the user device. One option is to rely on the Multipoint Control Unit (MCU) function, which combines and processes the video captured from various users in order to reduce the resource requirements of the clients. It performs Session Control functions for the scene configuration, network media processing and common sense media. The server processes the audio streams from the participants together with the motion signals, relative positioning, and location information. In the end, this creates the XR experience

and makes it possible for users to form smaller groups for discussion within the XR space, as it would happen in a real environment.

Figure 7.1.6: XR Conference [2]

7.1.7 Spatial Audio Multiparty Call

Finally, this scenario represents an AR multiparty call where each party can see the other parties using 2D video streams captured by the front facing camera of a mobile phone. Its layout is depicted in Figure 7.1.7.

Figure 7.1.7: Spatial Audio Multiparty Call [2]

7.2 Proposed Use cases

The proposed use cases are defined according to the resources' management perspective, either regarding radio resources, e.g. in the uplink congestion avoidance (UC1); or regarding other core resources to help determine the edge node selection (UC2).

In both cases, a holographic session is established across users and the aim is to adapt its setup or configuration so as to provide the best quality to the end users participating

in these sessions. To that end, the Holographic Orchestrator can adapt the preparation and delivery of the multimedia content required for the holographic sessions following different approaches: (i) the Selective Forwarding Unit (SFU) forwarding all incoming streams to the rest of the clients of the session with 1 stream in UL and N-1 streams in DL per client; or (ii) the Multipoint Control Unit (MCU), and potentially the SFU too, where the MCU multiplexes and fuses all streams from a given session, as well as performing smart transcoding so that every client receives a single personalized stream through the SFU. In both experiments, the followed approach is the one provided in the first option, with the SFU.

7.2.1 Uplink congestion avoidance

In this use case, multiple users are requesting holographic sessions and are either served with the same or different 5G cells. The required media processing modules (e.g. MCU and SFU) are deployed on the cloud to ensure a seamless XR experience. Besides this, the Holographic Orchestrator is also deployed on the cloud for session control and management, as shown in Fig. 7.2.1.

Figure 7.2.1: Proposed use case diagram for UL congestion avoidance

The red box named “Congestion detection and control function” is a function that needs to be implemented and has the capability to identify which user’s flow(s) in the UL direction is causing congestion and notifies the Holographic Orchestrator to take an action to relieve the congestion. This function can be an API pulling the user’s flow ID and its traffic and decide on them the congestion status. The events that can lead to congestion can be either the addition of new holo users or upgrading the resolution for active users, currently connected to holographic sessions.

7.2.2 Best Edge selection

Similar to the first use case, the second use case features multiple users establishing holographic sessions from their capture systems and against the Holographic Orchestrator. Depending on the topology of the network, the media volumetric flows can travel through the same (UC2.1) or different (UC2.2) cells. Also, depending on the edge and network specific considerations, the processed media flows are forwarded back to the user from the SFU in one or other edge.

Note:

- SFU can be located in any edge and selected for use based on edge conditions.

Figure 7.2.2.1: Edge selection based on edge conditions (UC2.1)

In this regard, two sub use cases will be evaluated in terms of interest and feasibility, and one of these will be selected: (a) UC2.1, where edge-specific conditions are contemplated for the edge selection, such as the computational, memory, disk or network usage, as well as the availability of specific resources such as GPU – as depicted in Fig. 7.2.2.1; and (b) UC2.2, where the user location is used to determine the closest edge in use, users can connect through different cells and one or more SFUs can be either distributed across the edges or next to the 5G core – as shown in Fig. 7.2.2.2.

Note:

- SFU can be located in any edge and selected for use based on network conditions.

Figure 7.2.2.2: Edge selection based on network conditions (UC2.2)

The Holographic Orchestrator runs at the cloud, whereas the Edge Orchestrator and the QoS/SLA Evaluator may run at the cloud (pictured) or at the edges, as it is more

optimal for the edge-specific data extraction. Each edge has a specific SFU (in charge of forwarding streams) which can be either (i) pre-provisioned and selected for usage, or (ii) directly requested for provisioning; both following an on-demand approach.

The red box named "QoS/SLA Evaluator" will be a function (interacting with, or part of the Edge Orchestrator) that operates on the metadata exposed by the Edge Orchestrator, which in turn, extracts data from the edge platform available in each edges in order to understand the edge's exposed capabilities (e.g. availability of GPU) as well as its current runtime status (e.g. network bandwidth or CPU consumption). The information on QoS/SLA allows the Holographic Orchestrator to retrieve some intelligence on the most adequate edge to use for selection or deployment of a given SFU instance through its session managers, with the ultimate goal of optimally connecting a new user to the holographic session.

8. Conclusión

This deliverable has presented the state of the art XR services and the 3GPP reference architecture in the 5G system. Moreover, it explored the network requirements. This

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deliverable also provided a detailed description of the project's two use cases planned to be trialed during the project regime. It also listed all the requirements considering the use cases of the 6G OPENVERSO-NET project.

9. References

[1] 3GPP, TS 26.501 v.18.3.1, "5G Media Streaming (5GMS); General description and architecture." Accessed 2023.

[2] 3GPP, TR 26.928 V18.0.0 , "Extended Reality (XR) in 5G," Accessed 2023.